

Problem Behaviours: From Assessment to Treatment of Behavioural Crises

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Abstract

Psychological development is characterised by a progressive change in the interaction between the individual and environmental events, which together determine a continuous exchange of influences. Among these interactions, problem behaviours that are not considered relevant to the context in which the individual operates also serve a “functionally adaptive” role. This type of behaviour generally disrupts learning and socialisation, creating situations of discomfort that the individual learns to use to exercise control over their environment. In this way, they develop “strategies” (problem behaviours) through which they can regulate and/or influence events in the context.

However, this obstructive and disruptive role in development is not always evident, especially when viewed from a strict psychopathological perspective.

Introduction

Problem behaviours are behaviours that disrupt an individual's learning and socialisation process, leading to uncomfortable situations that are learned to exert control over the environment. They may initially emerge in a specific context and under contingencies, then be maintained due to associated secondary effects. In other words, severe problem behaviours develop gradually through shaping responses, mainly via social contingencies.

Assessment should therefore focus on identification and maintenance factors: 1) identifying early types of behaviour that share similar aspects with severe problem behaviours but may be less intense and do not cause, for example, tissue damage (lightly banging the head on objects, biting without leaving teeth marks, scratching without necessarily breaking the skin, pulling hair, etc.), called “pre-maladaptive behaviours”, and 2) demonstrating that these acts are related to environmental contingencies: the same behaviour can have different functions depending on the antecedent conditions [1-4].

These considerations highlight the challenge educators (parents or teachers) encounter in identifying the possible causes (antecedents) that trigger the

problematic response. These conditions can be categorised based on three criteria:

1. *Temporal proximity*: situations that are close in time to the problem behaviour and for which a functional analysis is easier than for “distant” ones.
2. *The type*: conditions that can influence the manifestation of a problem behaviour and are defined as “setting events”.
3. *The influence* indicates the facilitating role of motivating conditions (the individual “activates” positively or negatively to achieve a goal) and those *oriented towards action* (the individual is “activated” by “external suggestions”).

The functional effects produced by responses are certainly not aimed at maintaining problem behaviour, but they can contribute to its consolidation through operant learning mechanisms (positive and negative reinforcement). These mechanisms allow the observation of the contingencies described by functional analysis.

Functional Analysis

The term “functional analysis”, first used by [5] refers to the study of the relationship between antecedent events, behaviour, and consequences to predict and manage classes of behaviour. It has been utilised in two distinct ways: 1) the impact that a behaviour has on the

More Information

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environment, and 2) the relationship between two variables where one depends on the presence or absence of the other.

Functional analysis methods were further developed by behaviour analysts to identify functionally equivalent response alternatives [6] and to regulate antecedent stimuli [7], aiming to create more effective behavioural support programmes [8], to discuss key points for procedure implementation and operational definitions (A-B and A-B-C models, indirect assessment, descriptive or analogous analysis, etc.), and ultimately, to refine experimental techniques, which vary considerably in many aspects [9-12]. In essence, the functional analysis methodology, by identifying the contingencies that maintain a problem behaviour, the associated discriminative stimuli (Sd), and the motivational contextual conditions, reaffirms the importance of applied research for understanding the determinants of behaviour [8,10,13]. Behaviour, observed along a temporal continuum, is caused by situations that precede it, called antecedent or stimulus situations, and is reinforced by the consequences that such behaviour produces. Therefore, identifying the elements that precede and follow the behaviour will facilitate the development of intervention strategies capable of changing them and, consequently, modifying the behaviour of the individual under observation.

The results thus achieved can be used in three ways [12]:

- 1) Eliminate or reduce the triggers, or antecedent conditions, that maintain the behaviour.
- 2) Eliminate the reinforcement contingency by removing or manipulating all maintenance reinforcers.
- 3) Reverse the contingencies (the reinforcers that uphold the problem behaviour contingent on alternative behaviours [14,15].

Treatment based on these principles, although highly effective and non-aversive, can be challenging to implement due to the following limitations of functional analysis [16]:

- 1) It is not always possible to identify the function of the problem behaviour,
- 2) Multiple factors may influence the behaviour,
- 3) The problem behaviour is not susceptible to extinction,
- 4) Reinforcers are challenging to eliminate (automatic responses from others), and
- 5) The behaviour may be maintained by sensory reinforcers that are very difficult to extinguish.

Within a functional analysis context, it is possible to find solutions, albeit partial, to these limitations, including:

- 1) Contingent control of attention to the meta-behaviour, as opposed to non-contingent control of attention to the target behaviour,
- 2) Non-contingent reinforcement,

- 3) Fading procedures,

- 4) Environmental enrichment,

- 5) Competition between reinforcement of the appropriate behaviour and the problem behaviour [15]. If these strategies fail, then treatment must be applied independently of the functions of the problem behaviour: response blocking, punishment, or differential reinforcement [2].

Over the last forty years, there has been an enormous spread of functional analysis as a tool for understanding problem behaviours and intervening on them [9,17-21], providing methods for testing the hypothesis that problem behaviours are maintained by specific and systematic antecedents and consequences that occur in the person's environment. There are three distinct techniques of functional analysis [3,22,23]: 1. informative/indirect assessment (clinical interview), 2. direct observation of antecedents and consequences in the person's natural environment, 3. experimental manipulation of the antecedents and consequences believed to be responsible for the problem behaviour, creating "analogous situations" to those of the main functions.

The procedures for applying functional analysis require a high level of competence on the part of the observers, who, for these reasons, often refrain from using it (especially parents and teachers).

This model of functional analysis (antecedents, behaviour, consequences), considering that human behaviour is a function of internal antecedents (particular psychological states that can act as triggers for the appearance of specific behaviours), unconditioned external antecedents (present stimulus situations that activate specific responses) and conditioned external antecedents (past stimulus situations that can act as conditioned stimuli for specific behavioural responses) simultaneously, requires a richer and more articulated theoretical reference model. Functional analysis must therefore investigate both the factors that frequently manifest themselves around the problem behaviour and those that manifest themselves in support of adaptive behaviours. This aspect is essential, as educational intervention should never be aimed solely at extinguishing inappropriate behaviours, but should also stimulate the emergence of adaptive behaviours. Unacceptable behaviours are, in most cases, the only (or one of the few) tools that children with atypical development have at their disposal to manage their environment and obtain gratification [24].

Understanding the function of problem behaviour, therefore, allows us to regulate and control a behavioural crisis constructively.

The Behavioural Crisis

As is easy to understand, through repeated associations between events (antecedents and consequences), the

individual learns to use behaviour to exercise control over their environment: that is, they know “strategies” (problem behaviours) through which they can regulate and/or control events in the context [25]. These processes of regulation and control seem to involve: 1) personal satisfaction (self-affirmation); 2) access to otherwise unattainable reinforcers; 3) an “escape route” from unsustainable situations; 4) greater sensory “activation”; 5) a “shift” of attention away from endogenous causes; 6) a mode of communication; 7) a conditioned response to events that occurred in other contexts and times; 8) “counter-control” [25]. These implications are not mutually exclusive, but may all be relevant to the same behaviour. Therefore, it is necessary not only to understand the reasons behind specific manifestations but also the antecedent and consequent conditions that lead to the “explosion” of the behavioural crisis (by “behavioural crisis” we mean a physical, motor, emotional, etc., response that is unplanned and involuntary, evoked to cause harm to oneself, others, or objects in response to specific environmental contingencies [3]. Often destructive towards oneself and others and difficult to control, it represents the true and only “problem behaviour” that most concerns teachers, parents, and therapists. Behavioural crises always indicate a high degree of suffering on the part of the individual exhibiting them, regardless of how the crisis manifests itself. They therefore require intervention, both in terms of containment (what to do when they occur) and prevention (to avoid or at least reduce their frequency and intensity), which must be paced, modulated, and regulated through the following phases [26]:

Phase 0: control. The subject performs activities they enjoy normally, without displaying behavioural changes or causing damage to objects and/or people.

Phase 1: pre-activation. Behavioural changes can be seen compared to phase 0, but there is no damage to objects or people. *Suggestions:* During this phase, the educator should try to identify behavioural changes from phase 0 and explore possible solutions (e.g., calibrate effort, maintain instructions and guide responses, switch to simpler instructions if needed but always return to the original instructions, etc.) to prevent potential risks (such as escalation of the crisis: a rapid shift to later phases until an “explosion”).

Phase 2: activation. Any antecedent event (internal or external) that triggers the maladaptive behaviour; this mechanism is often responsive, so it should be sought in the *setting events* and the subject's personal history. *Suggestions:* in this phase, to counteract the effect of the antecedents, the educator should: 1) continuously and positively reinforce all appropriate behaviours adopted; 2) stimulate the subject's interest and participation in the proposed activities; 3) make the tasks requested “pleasant”; 4) use activities compatible

with the subject's chronological age; 5) individualise the intervention by helping the subject in the various learning modes.

Phase 3: intensification. The behavioural response that has been activated, lacking sufficient coping strategies, becomes more intense. The duration of this phase can range from a few seconds to several hours, depending on the prolongation of certain stressful events (in terms of frequency, duration, and intensity) and the build-up of unmet motivational needs.

Suggestions: during this phase, in which the problem behaviour begins to increase in frequency, the educator, to prevent the subject's behaviour from progressing to the third and most problematic phase, should: 1) prevent the problem behaviour from being followed by intrinsic reinforcers; 2) provide the same reinforcers for incompatible behaviour; 3) establish a solid bond with the subject; 4) anticipate what is about to happen to the subject to enhance their coping strategies; 5) prevent the problem behaviour from being carried out completely; 6) use relaxation procedures or strategies (music, play, walking, lying down for a few minutes on a bed, etc.).

Phase 4: explosion. The crisis reaches its peak with often destructive or self-destructive behaviours, in which the subject can no longer process external information. In this phase, the intervention of others, typically drawn by the commotion and shouting, can only worsen the subject's distress, further intensifying or prolonging the crisis.

Suggestions: this is the most intense phase, during which the educator should: 1) avoid extrinsic reinforcers; 2) employ positive punitive procedures only in cases of highly destructive behaviour towards themselves or others (these procedures, due to their level of aversiveness, should be used with great caution and solely when less restrictive methods are completely ineffective [4,26]; 3) maintain a calm and protective attitude; 4) safeguard others by removing them from the situation and mitigating the physical consequences of the problematic behaviour; 5) only in cases of dangerous behaviour and as a last resort, seek assistance from other staff members trained in crisis management.

Stage 5: attenuation. Gradually, after reaching a peak, and if not supported by other events, the crisis begins to diminish, and the subject appears to regain some control over the contextual variables. However, at this stage, a *reintensification* of the crisis is possible if certain environmental factors intervene.

Suggestions: in this phase, characterised by the possibility that the crisis may either subside or reoccur, the educator should: 1) gradually guide the individual towards adaptive behaviours using shaping techniques; 2) positively and differentially reinforce competitive and functionally analogous behaviours; 3) establish

empathetic interaction; 4) remove other people from the setting; 5) adopt relaxation procedures (listening to music, having the individual lie down on a couch, etc.).

Phase 6: recovery. The subject returns to a *pre-activation* phase where they can once again process external information. However, this phase does not rule out the possibility that the subject may “reactivate” again in the short term for another crisis.

Suggestions: In this final phase, to reduce the risk of new behavioural crises, the educator should: 1) enhance the subject's interpersonal relationships; 2) teach new skills that compete with the problematic behaviours; 3) reinforce adaptive activities that the subject spontaneously produces; 4) share common interests; 5) teach reinforcement delay and frustration tolerance; 6) implement intervention strategies based on self-control and communication procedures.

The suggestions marked for crisis management do not qualify as educational interventions, but rather as methods for temporarily controlling dangerous situations. In contrast, intervention is a long-term educational process that encourages the learning of new skills that “replace” the problem behaviour [27] It should no longer focus on merely modifying behaviour (by using techniques to reduce the frequency, duration, and intensity of problem behaviours). Instead, as functional analysis procedures have demonstrated, it should aim to teach functionally equivalent behaviours, which are *substitute* behaviours that enable the individual to achieve the same goals as engaging in maladaptive behaviour.

Educational Treatment

Once the target behaviours had been defined, the initial behavioural interventions involved developing a treatment programme that, using specific techniques, reduced the frequency, duration, and intensity of the problem behaviours. Now, through functional analysis procedures, it has been understood that problem behaviour can serve different purposes, and consequently, other intervention strategies are necessary. From this perspective, the approach to intervene on problem behaviour has changed significantly: intervention on problem behaviour, such as aggression, is only carried out to manage crises and ensure the safety of the individual and others, while the actual treatment focuses on teaching positive behaviours—*substitute* behaviours that enable the individual to achieve the same goals as those pursued through maladaptive behaviour.

The operational procedures for conducting an appropriate psychoeducational intervention for problem behaviours should be divided into the following phases, with each “point” representing a specific intervention [28]:

Phase I [anticipation of the problem behaviour]: 1) gradually introduce the person to the situation that triggers the antecedent stimulus for the problem behaviour (approach the situation step by step, gradually moving closer to the normal situation); 2) increase the individual's motivation to engage in task-oriented activities (using extrinsic reinforcement); 3) strengthen coping skills (social and communication skills); 3) eliminate conditions that produce maladaptive responses (e.g., performance demands that are not fully mastered); 4) provide suitable alternatives (social competence, behaviour control, and regulation).

Phase II [replacement of problem behaviour]: 1) identify and define positive behaviours that are *functionally equivalent* to the problem behaviour (appropriate for the chronological age, socially accepted and not interfering with other learning); 2) “model” the replacement behaviours, in the direction of the goal, exploiting the subject's motivational drive (reinforce every “hint” of the behaviour to be acquired); 3) positively reinforce the replacement behaviour (once the goal has been achieved, extrinsic reinforcement should be gradually reduced, giving way to natural reinforcement); 4) inhibit the behaviour being “replaced” if it suddenly reappears (prevent the behaviour from being performed entirely, but allow it to be emitted; if the behaviour is dangerous to oneself or others, it must be stopped);

Phase III [non-contingent reinforcement]: 1) generalise (in various contexts, situations, and with different people, beyond the initial setting) and sustain (in the individual's behavioural repertoire) the replacement behaviour; 2) increase the learning opportunities the individual creates independently (reinforcing spontaneous behaviours that pursue appropriate goals); 3) enhance social competence (interacting with others on an equal basis); 4) positively influence relationships with the environment (creating new opportunities for communication and interaction). This educational programme can be delivered in two ways. The first is informal, where strategies for managing problem behaviour are introduced as it occurs. The second method, however, involves a formal series of structured interventions customised to the individual's abilities (strengths and weaknesses). In any case, individuals must be encouraged in such a way that they initiate the intervention.

Based on these considerations, the educator should unconditionally accept all behaviours exhibited by the subject to increase the number of behaviours to be reinforced and to build an effective helping relationship. At the same time, however, they should observe and manage the behaviour to develop new adaptive skills, promoting inclusion in the classroom.

The Inclusion of a Student with Autism in the Classroom

Many behaviours should be taught in natural environments (where they would normally occur). Suppose the goal is to train individuals to act as independently as possible in community life. In that case, educators must move away from relying solely on a “simulated” teaching model and instead adopt a “functional” approach: for example, to achieve the goal of “improving fine motor skills”, the strategy of “manipulating plasticine” (a non-functional activity) should be replaced with “opening the front door with a key” (a functional activity). The belief that certain non-functional activities are necessary for children to handle more complex tasks remains common among educators and leads to “fragmented” learning that lacks practical application in daily life. As a result, a child may be able to insert pegs into a pegboard but struggle to insert a key into a lock.

Effective interaction between adults and individuals with autism is a valuable resource that should be utilised by educators to encourage the desired behaviour. Maintaining a positive relationship is crucial for achieving constructive changes in the child's behaviour and for fostering training in the following areas: 1) eliminating adverse emotional reactions, 2) increasing motivation, 3) valuing social reinforcement more highly, 4) promoting communication, and 5) strengthening interpersonal relationships.

Educational intervention in the classroom, mediated by a specialised teacher, should occur at two distinct levels. The first targets individualised learning to develop all the preparatory and curricular skills of the student, which is standard practice. The second focuses on ‘peer resources’ to enhance social competence, functional communication, and the diversification of interests and activities. Several studies [28-30] have shown that peers can successfully implement incidental teaching strategies to increase mutual interactions with classmates who have autism. This approach is vital because it indicates that “free training” techniques are not only effective but can also be carried out by peers. This group has significant potential to bring about behavioural changes in their peers, especially in social skills, such as language and attention.

The effectiveness of this kind of intervention could be enhanced if teachers applied an educational programme designed to:

- Encourage the child to focus on other classmates.
- Using peers as role models to encourage appropriate behaviour.
- Encouraging peer imitation.
- Focusing on the child's learning and continuously encouraging interaction.
- Helping them to express what they need.
- Focusing on “sitting still” during lessons.

- Reinforcing the child and their peers when they display suitable interactive behaviours.
- Try to eliminate the child's rigidity by not allowing them to always play with the same objects and in the same order.
- Do not permit the child to use inappropriate behaviour to gain attention.
- Confront challenging situations but focus on helping the child with their difficulties and fostering their abilities.

In any case, the authors have been working for several years to develop a comprehensive classroom integration programme, which is implemented before the steps mentioned above. It comprises the following phases:

Phase 1. Before being integrated into the class, the student with autism interacted with only one other child (in a smaller environment and with a classmate they already knew or with whom a teacher-mediated pairing process was initiated) for about a week, gradually increasing the duration to one hour or more.

Phase 2. The same situation as in Phase 1 was repeated with two other children, who alternated with the previous one for another week. In both this phase and the previous one, access to reinforcers was unrestricted.

Phase 3. During this week-long phase, the teacher implemented planned activities “using” the classmates as tutors. Reinforcers were delivered on a contingent basis, with daily half-hour sessions scheduled for the entire group in the classroom, promoting interaction among classmates.

Phase 4. The entire group was permanently integrated into the class, although activities outside the classroom could still be organised to strengthen interactions.

Phase 5. The child remained permanently in the class.

Conclusions

The educational pathways activated by the implementation of these phases, although differing across various curricular levels (nursery, primary, and secondary school), were nonetheless focused on acquiring personal and contextual skills. These skills enabled students, according to their abilities, to develop and strengthen their competencies in the school setting and to participate, even in other contexts, in group activities. They benefited from the same social experiences, regardless of their cognitive skills.

Furthermore, ten years of experience working with various children with autism has not only enhanced the social and interpersonal skills of these children but has also promoted prosocial behaviour among their classmates and increased the willingness of both teachers and parents of other children in the class.

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